

GENERAL FACTORS COLLABORATING TO INEFFECTIVE EDUCATION AND LEARNING IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS: WHY ARE SCHOOLS IN DECADENCE?

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Abstract

The study sought to explore factors that contribute towards effective teaching and learning in primary schools. The study was prompted by high failure rate of pupils at grade seven level which entire zero percent pass rate since 2013. The researchers were prompted to explore why there is such decay in schools in Zimbabwe. Mixed methods were used to collect data. The study found out that teachers do not employ a variety of teaching methods do not prepare a variety of media for use in the teaching and learning. Teachers' instructional materials are limited to textbooks and timetable and do not go beyond that. Pupils learn in severe and uncondusive teaching and learning environments and there is low state among teachers.

Key words: teaching, learning, effective teaching and learning, pedagogical practices.

1. Conceptual structure

Effective learning is hard to define. It is argued that effective teaching is phenomenal for raising student achievement [1, 15]. Lorin 2006 suggested that effective teaching is one that creates demonstrable results in terms of the denotatively and affective development of the students and thus it is an important component in every teaching professional. It is argued that effective teaching involves far more than presenting content and systems used to convey that content. Equally important are the affective or emotional processes involved in

education, the combination and application of new data and social structure that take place between individuals and their environment. The primary significance of the hierarchy is to identify prerequisites that should be completed to provision learning at each degree. Prerequisites are identified by doing a task analysis of learning/training task. Learning hierarchies provide a basis for the stringing of structure.

Literature

Effective teaching is deliberated as a privacy by some authors [2 ,2]) in their education on the synthesis of research on good teaching identified that effective teachers are obvious about their instructional goals, are knowledgeable about the content, communicate well, monitor students' understanding, are thoughtful and respectful about their teaching practices. School climate contributes towards school effectiveness. Scientist notes that school climate has an impact on the performance of teachers in the school. It is argued that the way an personal or a person in an organization performs is prescribed by the organizations setting, in this case its climate. In a school where there is no raised between school leadership and teachers the climate is conducive for valid teaching and learning. This should point out that inadequate materials such as textbooks within the home rational and lowly educated parents should not be regarded as a total action in pupils' poor performance in rustic primary schools. The diverse individual aptitude of pupils should also be taken into consideration. Within the poor background may be born a genius. In addition it is not always only the performers from low income families who tend to be ineffective as far as academic attainment is concerned. Some children from even rich families may also perform academically poor due to other causes though indigent performers among children from well to do families are tenuous. Time direction is raised as a factor that contributes latterly ineffective teaching. Some students are always out on sports. All play no work negatively effects on school performance. It is important for

teachers to control their time and cover the whole syllabus so that students gain adequate content to tackle inspection.

Speculative framework: Provisions of learning theory Robert Gagne

The theory on circumstances of learning was propounded by Robert Gagne and the theory stipulates that there are several different types or levels of learning. It emphasizes the importance of the classifications in that each different type requires different types of instruction. Gagne recognize five major categories of learning which include among others, verbal information, intellectual skills, cognitive strategies, motor skills and experiences. The theory advances that diverse internal and external conditions are necessary for each type of studying[3,63].

Conclusions

Section of the population with background contributes to teacher effectiveness. Teachers teaching pedagogy influence effective teaching. Explanation and demonstration are useful in the teaching and learning. Grouping pupils according to ability for promotes teacher effectiveness. School based factors contribute to teacher effectiveness. Friendly atmosphere in an organization contribute to teacher effectiveness. Children from literate parents seemed to be more influence to teacher. Variety teaching learning materials in scheming and planning promote effective teaching. Dissimilart interrogations systems promote teachers performances.

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